

**TIQ FLASH ADC DESIGN IMPLEMENTED BY USING THE ICG AND LOW POWER
MUX BASED ENCODER TECHNIQUES****Chanakya Dhaani**Research Scholar, GAT, Bangalore -560098
chanakya.dharani@gmail.com**Dr. Ravi J**

Professor, Dept. of ECE, GAT, Bangalore -560098

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Abstract— Analog-to-digital converter (ADC) based on CMOS Flash and Threshold Inverter Quantization (TIQ) for system-on-chip (SoC) applications. TIQ technology uses two cascaded CMOS inverters as voltage comparators. However, this TIQ technology must evolve with the latest SoC trends, which require the ADC to be integrated on-chip with other digital circuits, with a focus on low-power, low-voltage implementations. TIQ comparators minimize the effects of process, temperature and supply voltage fluctuations. The TIQ Flash ADC achieves has a higher speed and resolution. TIQ Flash reduces or controls ADC power consumption. You can save a lot of energy by controlling the power consumption of the comparator. The new comparator also has great advantages over TIQ comparators in reducing power consumption and noise. The results demonstrated that the modified multi-base TIQ flash ADC operates with small size, reduced power consumption, and lower voltage than existing flash ADCs while achieving quick conversion. The proposed method presents a new ICG based design methodology that also reduces dynamic power in the power domain.

Index Terms— Encoder, Flash ADC, Threshold Inverter Quantization, ICG .

I. INTRODUCTION

In 2018, a transistor's minimum channel length was lowered to 0.007 μm in accordance with the Semiconductors Road Map. Additionally, the current System-on-Chip (SoC) trend demands the integration of analogue and digital Integrated Circuits (ICs) into a single chip known as a complete SoC. Wireless networking (WLAN, voice/data LAN), consumer electronics, and broadband communications all currently have considerable demand for entire SoC (DVD, MP3, digital cameras, videogames, etc.). Therefore, Analog-to-Digital Converters (ADCs), one of the mixed-signal ICs, must follow to this overall SoC trend. Potential ADC and semiconductor technology design issues for the overall SoC trend are presented in this analysis. Using a complete adder-based encoder is a typical method for encoding a thermometer code [1].

A full adder-based encoder only contains a full adder. For a full adder-based chip level, this full adder is built on a low-power design with low area consumption. Noise linearity is also reduced as a useful method of reducing TIQ based comparator power leakage. With each successive nanometer technology, the sub-threshold voltage declines, and enhances leakage current. Developing data

converters using the same technology as the rest of the chip is required for high-performance integrated semiconductor systems like System-on-a-Chip. Applications need data converter development to meet their linearity requirements, save power consumption, or increase bandwidth at the same time.

The world needs low power data converters built with advanced technology in the age of rapidly expanding smartphone usage, ever-faster connection speeds, and the development of wearable electronics and portable health care products. Depending on the specifics of their designs, designers choose for several forms of ADC. Flash ADC is desirable because of its high conversion speed, although it has limits due to its high cost and maintenance. Flash ADC is an extremely effective encoder that uses TIQ and consumes little power[3]. The structure's major goal is to lower its energy. A TIQ comparator creates a code that compares the input signal to a switching voltage that is internally created [4].

Flash ADCs have a wide range of uses, including radar receivers, digital prototypes, and LAN interface. A $2n$ bit to n bit encoder and $2n - 1$ voltage comparators make up a TIQ flash ADC [5]. All of the power and space are consumed by a flash ADC. In order to deal with the impacts of process, temperature, and voltage changes in the power supply, the TIQ comparator is used. To some extent, a noise reduction algorithm can distort the signal. Analog and digital signal processing equipment share noise-sensitive features. High speed and resolution TIQ Flash ADCs are required. ADC power loss is reduced or controlled by TIQ Flash. By controlling the comparator's power dissipation, it offers significant power conservation. As a result, the proposed ICG based flash ADC design architecture minimizes design area, simplifies noise, and saves power.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

This approach provides a survey of alternative flash ADC design methodologies. Various CMOS technologies and bits have been used by researchers to implement Flash ADC.

Jincheol Yoo, Kyusun Choi, Jahan Ghaznavi et al. [2]: The Quantum Voltage (QV) comparator, a new voltage comparator design, is made available by this technique for the deep sub-micron low voltage CMOS Flash A/D Converter (ADC) of the future generation. To demonstrate low voltage functionality, the new QV comparator was created and simulated. The 6-bit and 8-bit QVC Flash ADCs both work properly, are highly efficient, and operate quickly. The QV comparator has a significant advantage when it comes to noise rejection and power consumption, as demonstrated by the simulation result with a power supply of 0.7 V.

Liyaqat Nazir , Roohie Naaz Burhan Khurshid and Mir et al.[1]: PDP, the area calculation based on the number of transistors, and the best and worst styles were chalked out in a comparison based on their estimated power consumption. The implementation of a 2 magnitude comparator is described using seven different approaches. This analysis led to the hybrid PTLICMOS logic style, which is utilized to change the best magnitude comparator.

S. S. KHOT et al [6]: An architecture based on a reduced comparator and multiplexer is provided for

a 4-bit CMOS-based flash ADC. The updated ADC in this instance has totally modified analogue and digital components. For a 4 bit ADC, this architecture only requires 4 comparators. Hspice is used to design and simulate this 4-bit ADC with a 1.2 V supply voltage.

Yoo, Jincheol, Kyusun Choi, and Ali Tangel et al. [7]: The 4 Bit Flash ADC is designed with a comparator that uses the TIQ technique. TIQ Comparator provided thermometer code and compared input signal with linearity-generated switching. A 2:1 multiplexer designed on transmission gates has been used to create an effective thermometer to binary converter. This design ran at an input frequency of 1k Hz at 800 mv.

Yao-Jen Chuang, Hsin-Hung Ou and Bin-Da Liu et al.[8]: A new digital encoder network known as the Pseudo-dynamic NMOS encoder is developed for use in the Flash ADC's modified TIQ-based architecture. The 4 bit Flash ADC is designed using a pseudo-dynamic NMOS encoder that outperforms all existing encoding networks. The new encoding network offers a 7 GS/s high data transport rate with minimal power requirements.

Tangel Ali and Kyusun Choi et al. [9]: Utilizing Domino Logic's Current Comparison-Based Comparator. When compared to a standard domino circuit, the 64 bit comparator simulation results show a 51 percent power reduction for 64 bit comparator consumption and simulation time. This comparator was constructed utilizing a 22nm high performance predictive technology model.

Vudadh and Chetan et al. [10]: A low-power self-reconfigurable mux-based decoder with adaptive resolution utilizing flash ADC was reported. It provided Flash analog-to-digital converters with a new, improved multiplexer-based decoder. Based on a 2:1 mux, the proposed decoder computes the binary code for the short operand length thermistor code in the early stage and then combines the results of the initial stage to produce the final output. The final result is then produced by aggregating the outputs from the initial stages. Without adding any further overhead, the decoder may be set up to work with short resistor codes. Especially useful in adaptive resolution analog-to-digital converters is its " self-rebuildable" property. According to simulation data, the decoder for flash analog-to-digital converters produces less delay, power, and power delay than conventional digital decoders.

Y. Berg et al. [11]: Differential high speed ultra-low voltage pass transistor with Boolean logic is suggested. This analysis introduces high-speed, ultra-low voltage junction transistors When operating at a supply voltage as low as 200mV, pass transistors have a delay that is less than 6% that of standard CMOS transistors. The serial adders with high-voltage low-voltage can be implemented using the pass transistor logic that has been provided. Data that has been adjusted was collected using the 90nm TSMC CMOS process and Cadence.

Sall Erik, Mark Vesterbacka, and K. OlaAndersson et al. [12]: A study of digital decoders in flash analog-to-digital converters was proposed. Flash analog-to-digital converters study digital decoders. Calculating the decoder at the thermistor coded comparator output, for example, a walrus tree, is an attractive way to comprehend a decoder. A one-counter is faster and has global bubble error correction. Compared to the Wallace Tree decoder, the Tree decoder produced by folding with a

smaller size and a less complicated circuit path, allowing for more efficient design. With no additional bubble error correction, a Convolutional decoder introduces more error correction circuitry for roughly the same hardware cost as a Wallace tree decoder. A low bit error rate becomes important for applications because of this, in addition to making the Convolutional decoder attractive [16].

II. ICG based FLASH ADC

The input voltage is compared to a set of increasing reference voltages in a flash ADC using a comparator array. The encoder's input binary output code is represented by the comparators' output. Using the inputs as a basis, an encoder generates a digital output. In a flash ADC implementation, the TIQ technique differs from the conventional technique in how the reference voltages are set. Using a resistor array structure and an array of comparator cells, the resistive Flash ADC compares the input voltage to the reference voltage to generate thermometer code. In the TIQ technique, the (W/L) ratio used to internally set the reference voltage is unique to each comparator. As a comparator, the TIQ technique makes use of two pairs of cascaded CMOS inverters. This technique proposed to be improved in order to be more effectively used in SoC applications. When compared to conventional Flash ADCs, the TIQ method reduces both the area of the ADC chip and the amount of power required. The architecture of Flash ADC, also known as parallel ADC, is faster than all Flash ADC.

Figure 3.1 Flash ADC.

TIQ Comparator:

The comparator is the most important part of the ADC design. It analyzes the reference voltage V_{ref} to the input voltage V_{in} in order to convert V_{in} to a logic "1" or "0." The comparator's output is "1" if V_{in} exceeds V_{ref} and "0" otherwise. Here, a reference voltage for comparison is the CMOS switching voltage[10]. It contains two CMOS inverters placed back-to-back and linked in series with the same channel width ($W_n=W_p$) ratio. When input and output voltages are equal ($V_{in}=V_{out}$), the CMOS inverter's switching threshold is reached, and both nMOS and pMOS transistors are thus permanently operating in the saturation region. Figure 3.3 shows the comparator threshold voltage after equating the equations.

Figure 3.2 : TIQ Flash ADC.

Figure 3.3 TIQ Comparator.

TIQ ICG Based Flash ADC:

The clock's extensive switching activity uses a lot of dynamic power. Clock gating is one method for lowering dynamic power use. A load enabled comparator only experiences output changes when enable is turned on. But, the clock switches constantly, increasing the dynamic power consumption. The conversion of load enable circuits to clock gating circuits helps lower dynamic power usage. As shown in Figure 3.5, a basic clock gating circuit consists of an AND gate with one input activated. However, a failure happens when the enable crosses over to the clock's positive level. An integrated clock gate is also utilized to remove the gate's interruptions. According to Figure 3.6, it comprises of an AND gate and a negative induced latch. As shown in Figure 3.3, a current flash ADC is combined with an integrated clock gating approach to significantly lower dynamic power usage.

Figure 3.4: TIQ ICG based Flash ADC.

Figure 3.5: Clock gating

Figure 3.6: ICG Circuit.

4. ENCODERS

Several encoders are available to convert thermometer code to gray code.

Fat tree encoder:

A fat tree-based encoder can convert thermometer code to grey code more efficiently. In comparison to a Wallace tree-based encoder, it has a reduced amplitude and delay. Additionally, this encoder has a self-configurable quality. In general, fat tree encoding consists of two steps: To begin, the thermometer code must be converted into one of n codes. The address decoder and output are the same for a one-out-of- n code. N bits are converted into codes simultaneously using N gates. The second phase uses a tree of several OR gates to convert the one-out-of- n code into binary code. For instance, the output Tree's root nodes generate a 4 Bit binary code, while the leaf nodes of the tree are introduced with a 15 bit one-out-of- n code. One can generalize from one tree to another and visualize the trees in three dimensions. One can imagine a 3-D visualization of the trees by identifying one tree to another. The number of edges on a node increases in response to the tree's height. Figure 4.1 shows how a fat tree-based encoder with 15-bit thermometer code input is implemented.

Figure 4.1 Fat tree encoder.

B. Full adder based encoder:

To cut down on power and delay, use an ADC with a transmission gate and op-amps in a full adder-based encoder [9]. Figure 4.2 shows how the Flash ADC uses op amps to reduce down on power consumption and delay.

Figure 4.2 Encoder using full adder transmission gates

C mux-based encoder:

Suggests a mux-based thermometer code to gray code encoder [9]. When compared to encoders based on Wallace and Fat trees, this encoder has a faster speed and a smaller area. Figure 4.3 shows the development of a MUX-based encoder for 15-bit thermometer code input.

Figure 4.3 mux-based encoder

D. Proposed 4 bit mux-based encoder

$$G4 = T8$$

$$G3 = T4T12$$

$$G2 = T2T6 + T6(T10T14)$$

$$G1 = T13T1 + T3(T7T5 + T7(T11T9 + T11(T15T13)))$$

Figure 4.4 shows the proposed design's architecture. The fundamental components of the proposed design are a 2:1 MUX for a 4-bit encoder and a 2-input XOR gate. A two-input XOR gate is used to extract the binary output codes from the grey output codes, which are implemented using a 2:1 MUX.

In contrast to the present MUX-based design, a proportion of the input lines in this instance are connected to the "1" ground terminal. As a result, less MUXs are required, and additional inverters are not required. To achieve low power consumption and minimal area, the 2:1 MUX and 2 input XOR gates are constructed in the transmission gate logic style.

Figure 4.4 Encoder using Proposed Mux based design

The T8 input thermometer code is the same as the G4 output grey code. So, T8 and G3 are directly connected. The input codes T12 and T4 are used to create the output code G3. Equivalent grey codes G1 are obtained with input codes T4, T4, T12 serves as an input to MUX 1, while T12 serves as a select line. The comparable grey code G2 is derived from the input codes T6, T2, T14, and T10. T10 and T2 are inputs to MUX 2 and 3, respectively, and T14 and T6 are used as select lines. MUX is used to create the output code G1 from the input codes T13, T15, T9, T11, T5, T7, T1, and T3. 4, 5, 6, 7. The output binary code is created from the grey code using the two input XOR gates. As a result, the same encoder can be utilized, and the proposed design also has the benefit of being self-reconfigurable. By setting the higher order inputs T8–T15 to “0,” the 4-bit encoder can be transformed into a 3-bit encoder. The inputs T4 through T15 can also be changed to a 2-bit encoder by setting them to '0'. The same encoder, for instance, can be used with a low-resolution flash ADC.

The design technique improved the ADC’s linearity with reference to variations in temperature, power supply voltage, and CMOS process. The speed limitation of all types of encoders, which is the potential bottleneck of high speed ADCs, was overcome by the modified mux based encoder. This analysis shows two changes to TIQ technology to achieve low power consumption and low voltage operation in addition to optimizing TIQ flash ADC performance. Flash ADC uses parallel voltage comparison, so when the ADC's resolution is increased, the power dissipation grows significantly. The TIQ Flash ADC uses both power and delay control techniques. Reduce power consumption at lower resolutions significantly to increase battery life. A new power management system can manage power usage on demand by adjusting the sample interval. TIQ flash ADCs are developed in CMOS technology for low voltage operation to validate functioning at low supply voltages. The TIQ flash ADC functioned successfully at high speeds with negligible linear error even without any additional circuitry. TIQ flash ADCs are smaller, quicker, and use less power than other ADCs. An integrated clock gating technique has also been used with this circuit to cut down on dynamic power.

5. SIMULATION RESULTS

The proposed Flash ADC offers superior performance and less power dissipation, as shown in Table 5.1. Compared to other Flash ADC, the current one has a low area. Figure 5.1 and Figure 5.2 both display bar charts for the latency and power dissipation of several Flash ADCs, respectively.

	Conventional Flash ADC	Full_adder based ADC	Mux based tiq Flash ADC	Modified mux based and ICG tiq Flash ADC
Technology	90nm	90nm	90nm	90nm
Resolution	4bit	4 bit	4 bit	4 bit
Supply voltage	1.1 V	1.1V	1.1 V	1.1 V
Delay	320.4ps	340ps	230ps	219ps
Power dissipation	732.2 mw	651.20 mw	612.021 mw	518.50 mw

Table 5.1 Results of different Flash ADC

Figure 5.1 Delay comparison of Flash ADC

Figure 5.2 Power dissipation of different Flash ADC

Figure 5.3 Simulation of TIQ ICG based Flash ADC

Figure 5.3's Flash ADC waveform has a 4 bit design. V_{in} is the analogue signal's input, and D0, D1, D2, and D3 are the corresponding digital outputs.

The designed TIQ ICG-based flash ADC technology reduces unnecessary resistive series and is utilized while developing a 4-bit ADC to produce grey code. The proposed TIQ ICG based flash ADC operates by minimizing the chip's surface area to regulate power dissipation. The simulation's results also compare it to the standard system and make recommendations. The New ICG Flash ADC approach reduced power dissipation by 518.50 mw compared to conventional Flash ADC of 732.2 mw. The ICG technique also results in a latency reduction of 219 ps as compared to the regular Flash ADC's 324.4 ps. The related graphs in Figures 5.1 and 5.2 show that adopting the proposed TIQ ICG-based flash ADC has an advantage in terms of delay time and power dissipation. The simulation results in Figure 5.3 display the 4-bit flash ADC waveform, where V_{in} is the analogue signal input corresponding to digital outputs D0, D1, D2, and D3. However, SoC applications are more specialized and advantageous for the proposed system.

6. CONCLUSION

The TIQ comparator supports in overcoming the effects of process, temperature, and voltage variations in the power supply. TIQ Flash ADCs with a higher resolution and speed are required. The TIQ Flash ADC managed and reduced power consumption. It provides in significant power reductions by regulating the comparator's power dissipation. The resistive array that is utilized to

build a 4-bit ADC that outputs grey code has been replaced with a new TIQ ICG based flash ADC. It is recommended to utilize a brand-new, power-saving mux-based encoder. Two pairs of cascaded CMOS inverters are used as comparators in the TIQ technique's proposed architecture, and each comparator is internally created with a (W/L) ratio to calculate the reference voltage. It was created to be more effectively implemented in SoC applications. When compared to conventional flash ADCs, TIQ technology helps minimize the size of the ADC chip, which in turn lowers power consumption. In an ADC architecture, a comparator compares an input voltage V_{in} to a reference voltage V_{ref} and converts it to a logical "1" or "0." As a result, the reference voltage for comparison is the CMOS switch voltage. When the input and output voltages are equal ($V_{in}=V_{out}$), CMOS inverters flip to the threshold state, and both the nMOS and pMOS transistors always function in the saturation region. Dynamic power consumption is significantly reduced with Flash ADC and combined clock gating. Therefore, this proposed ADC solution is appropriate for future SoC methodologies where high speed conversion and power with reduced area are the primary requirements. The New ICG Flash ADC technique reduces power dissipation is 518.50mw compared conventional Flash ADC as 732.2 mw and also less delay in ICG Technique 219ps compared conventional Flash ADC as 324.4ps. As a result, ICG-based Flash ADCs can benefit low-power applications. In subsequent steps, the mechanism of this converter could be improved by minimizing technological scaling.

7. REFERENCES

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